

Performance of solar absorber panel with reflector by response surface method

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ABSTRACT

This work maximized the performance of the black-chrome coated (B.C) and nickel-cobalt coated (Ni-Co) copper absorber panel. The reflectors were also use to maximize the incident solar radiation on the absorber. The flow rate, collector angle and reflector angle were chosen as the process variables and the thermal efficiency was considered as the response. The Box-Behnken method of experiments design and response surface method of optimization was carried out. This result reported that the coating on the absorber panel and reflectors used were improved the thermal efficiency of the solar flat plate collector. Compared to Ni-Co panel, Black-Chrome panel reported higher efficiency.

Keywords

Absorber panel, Black-Chrome coating, Box-Behnken, Nickel-Cobalt coating, Optimization, Reflectors, Response surface method.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The exponentially increasing need for renewable energies such as solar energy due to the government policies to reduce pollution and save the environment and replace the vanishing fossil fuels. Despite several methods to harvest solar energy, the simple and common method is the solar water heater. It uses a flat plate collector which converts the solar radiation into heat and the heat is observed by the fluid (Normally water). The thermal conversion of energy at low temperature such as solar flat plate collector (SFPC) is suitable for low and medium temperature range applications. But, has low relative efficiency [1].

Recent researches focusing on the enhancement of thermal efficiency of the solar water heater studied various methods of utilizing nano-fluids, phase change materials, reflectors, coating the absorber, altering the designs and materials. One of the major research subjects is to reduce the heat losses on the upper side of the collector to increase the heat utilization by proper design of the collector [2]. The general analysis of evaluation employed the heat loss coefficient and efficiency factor [3]. The examination of the effect of various process variables on thermal efficiency concluded that the optical properties of the absorber are highly influenced the coefficient of total heat loss [4].

The collector was redesigned with a corrugated absorber and recorded efficiency of 67% with 0.013 kg/s [5]. The triangle-shaped prototype SFPC has a high heat transfer area and showed 55% efficiency with 800 W/m² and 900 W/m² [6]. Research on the SFPC designed to take the water at the circumference of a spiral tube and leaves at the center reported that the solar radiation and flow rate of water highly influences the thermal efficiency of flat plate collector (FPC) [7]. The intensity of incident solar energy on the absorber area was enhanced by the flat reflectors [8]. The analysis of direct solar radiation and the combination of direct and reflected solar radiation was done by considering the variable reflector and collector angle [9]. A researcher used reflectors at either longer sides of the SFPC to reflect the direct and diffused radiation to

increase the intensity of radiation on the collector. They found that the efficiency was increased by 10% due to the reflectors [10].

Selective layer coating on the absorber was also analyzed by the researchers. The solar paints and black chrome coating were compared with the standard one. The results showed enhanced thermal performance. Further, higher emittance coating reduced the risk of overheating during the stagnation period [11]. Research on thermochromic layer on absorber reported the higher thermal efficiency up to 4.5% compared to conventional collector [12]. The optimization of black Nickel-Cobalt coating on absorber panel reported the improved optical properties which are required for improving the thermal efficiency of a collector [13]. A pure aluminum sheet with electroless Ni coating and Ni-pigmented anodized coatings showed a lower coefficient of emission and higher coefficient of absorption [14]. The absorber with TiAlC, TiAlCN, and TiAlSiCN layers with anti-reflecting (TiAlSiO) and semi-transparent (TiAlSiCO) layers was unstable when operating at higher temperatures [15].

The evolutionary algorithms such as response surface methodology were receiving attention in the last two decades in various fields [16]. The process variables were optimized by Taguchi and the grey relational method to improve the efficiency of SFPC [17]. Box-Behnken method of experiment design and response surface method of optimization is best suited for optimizing three process variables [18]. From the literature review, it is obvious that the effect of reflectors and selective layer coated absorbers in SFPC has not been examined. This work tried to operate the SFPC with maximum efficiency by optimization.

II. METHODS AND MEASUREMENT

One copper plate of 100 mm x 100 mm was electroplated for black-chrome and another was electro-plated for Ni-Co. These coatings were checked for solar absorptivity and emissivity. The electro-plating was detailed in [TABLE I](#).

TABLE I
TECHNICAL DATA FOR ELECTROPLATING

S.No.	Description	Black-Chrome plating	Nickel-Cobalt plating
1	Solution	CrCl ₃ -250 g/l CoCl ₂ - 14.1 g/l H ₂ SiF ₆ - 7.50 g/l NaH ₂ PO ₄ -3.80 g/l Naf - 19.7 g/l H ₂ O - 940 ml	NiSo ₄ - 300 g/l NiCl - 25 g/l H ₃ BO ₃ - 30 g/l Saccharin - 1 g/l MnSo ₄ - 5 g/l H ₂ O - 639 g/l
2	PH value of the solution	5.4	4
3	Temperature	20°C	24°C
4	Voltage (Tension)	4 V	5V
5	Current Density	2.5 A	4 A
6	Duration	150 Sec	120 Sec

The absorber panel used in this study was fabricated using 12.5 mm copper tubes of 2m as risers and 25mm tubes as headers. Copper strips of 50 mm X 1 mm were used as the fins. The collector (size 1500 mm x 500 mm x 150mm) is made of a GI sheet. The absorber panel was placed over the glass wool-filled box and was closed by the glass of 1500 mm x 500 mm x 4mm. This setup was built with hinges at both long sides to fix the glass reflector of size 1500 mm x 500 mm x 3 mm at any angle concerning the collector. The in and out water line has temperature sensors to measure the temperature and a rotameter to measure the flow rate. The setup was installed at Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India. It is geographically at latitude 11.0168°N, 76.9558°E.

The process variables namely volume flow rate of water (v°), Collector inclination (θ) and Reflector inclination (α), and the response thermal efficiency (η) were chosen. The experiments were planned as per the Box-Behnken approach of response surface methodology. The data collected were analyzed for their fitness and ANOVA was carried out to find the fitness of the model with the collected data. Using this regression model, the process variables were optimized for the maximum efficiency of the SFPC. The levels of the parameters used are presented in [TABLE II](#)

The first sets of experiments were conducted using the black-chrome coated panel and the second set of experiments used nickel-cobalt coated panel.

TABLE II
CONTROL VARIABLES AND THEIR LEVELS

S.No.	Variables	Units	Levels		
			Low (-1)	Medium (0)	High (+1)
1	The volume flow rate of water (v°)	l/min	0.5	1.5	2.5
2	Collector inclination (θ)	Degree	30	45	60
3	Reflector inclination (α)	Degree	30	45	60

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Optical Properties of the Electroplated Absorber

The solar absorptance and emittance were checked before and after electroplating. Copper has an absorptance of 0.68 and an emissivity of 0.09 before electroplating. The chromium oxides (Cr_2O_3) and crystalline structured chromium were present in the black chrome coating. But, their composition may vary across the area [19]. The absorptance was increased to 0.91 in black chrome coating and was 33.8% higher when compared to the non-coated copper. Similarly, the emissivity also doubled to 0.16. On the other side, Ni-Co coating has Ni (86.73 %) and Co (3.27 %) [20] and has 0.92 absorptance and 0.37 emittance. It was noted that the absorptance was increased by about 34%. The emittance of Ni-Co coating was significantly high and enhances the heat loss.

B. Design Surface of Variables – Black-Chrome Coated Panel

The optimization was carried out using Design Expert 7.0 software. The behavior pattern of the responses in both black-chrome and Ni-Co panels was almost the same. The ratio of maximum and minimum thermal efficiency was less than 3, which means no transformation of the response data needed to develop the model that fits with the data. The quadratic approximate model was selected based on the fitness level by the sequential sum of square type I. The deviations of the actual and predicted data were found by R-squared and Ra-squared values. These were ($R = 0.9944$, and $R_a = 0.9872$) closer to 1 and the difference between them was negligible. The ANOVA also ensures the fitness of the model for the confidence level above 95%. The normal plot of residuals Fig. 1(a) and the predicted and actual responses Fig. 1(b) as the deviation less than 5% and were evenly distributed either side of the line ensures the fitness. The normal plot of residuals and the responses (predicted and actual) were shown in Fig. 1.(a, b).

Fig. 1. (a) Normal probability vs. internally studentized residuals

(b) Predicted vs. actual responses for Black-Chrome coated panel

The response surface designed based on the derived regression model for black chrome coating was shown in Fig. 2 (a) and (b). Fig. 2(a) shows the interaction between the flow rate and the collector angle. At a lower flow rate and the collector angle records lower efficiency. The increase in these responses cause increase the efficiency to the maximum and further increases in these responses reduced the thermal efficiency. Similarly, Fig. 2 (b) shows the effect of interactions of flow rate

and the reflector angle. Fig. 2(c) shows the influence of the interaction of collector angle and reflector angle.

Fig. 2 Response surfaces of interactions for Black-Chrome coated panel (a) Flow rate vs. Collector angle, (b) Flow rate vs. Reflector angle, (c) Collector angle vs. Reflector angle

It is obvious from the discussion, all the three process variables in both the absorbers behave in the same manner. The lower value of the response shows the lower efficiency. Then, the efficiency was increased to a maximum with the process variable and further increase in process variable reduced the efficiency.

C. Design Surface of Variables – Nickel-Cobalt coated Panel

The observed data for Ni-Co panel was not required any transformation as the ratio of the maximum and minimum response was less than 3. The sequential sum of the square of type I suggested the quadratic polynomial to develop the regression model. The values of R and Ra were 0.9864 and 0.9439 which ensures the fitness of the model and data with the model. The ANOVA results have also assured the accuracy above 95% of confidence level. The plot of residuals was given in Fig. 3(a). and the predicted and actual responses were shown in Fig. 3(b).

Fig.3. (a) Normal probability vs internally studentized residuals, (b) Predicted vs actual responses for Nickel-Cobalt coated panel

The response surface designed based on the derived regression model was shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 4(a) shows the interaction between the flow rate and the collector angle. At a lower flow rate and the collector angle records lower efficiency. The increase in these responses increases the efficiency to the maximum and further increases in these responses reduced the thermal efficiency. The reason for this was already discussed in the previous section. Similarly, Fig. 4(b). shows the effect of

interactions of flow rate and the reflector angle. Fig. 4(c) shows the influence of the interaction of collector angle and reflector angle. It is obvious from the discussion, all the three process variables in both the absorbers behave in the same manner. The lower value of the response shows the lower efficiency. Then, the efficiency was increased to a maximum with the process variable and further increase in process variable reduced the efficiency.

Fig.4. Response surfaces of interactions for Nickel-Cobalt coated panel (a) Flow rate vs. Collector angle, (b) Flow rate vs. Reflector angle, (c) Collector angle vs. Reflector angle

D. Regression Models

The regression model developed for the response thermal efficiency of the SFPC with B.C coated absorber panel and Ni-Co coated panels were presented below.

$$TE_{(BC)} = -322.632 + 39.45V^\circ + 7.73783 \theta + 9.65783 \alpha - 0.210V^\circ \theta + 0.18V^\circ \alpha - 0.01388 \theta \alpha - 14.9675V^\circ{}^2 - 0.07796 \theta^2 - 0.10330 \alpha^2$$

$$TE_{(Ni-Co)} = -327.325 + 38.352 V^\circ + 7.60783 \theta + 9.61117 \alpha - 0.21000 V^\circ \theta + 0.1967 V^\circ \alpha - 0.01389 \theta \alpha - 14.8925 V^\circ{}^2 - 0.076522 \theta^2 - 0.103 \alpha^2$$

E. Optimization

The objective of this optimization was to maximize the thermal efficiency subjected to the constraints as follows.

Objective function

$$\text{Thermal Efficiency} = \text{maximize } f(x),$$

Subjected to

$$0.5 \text{ l/min} \leq \text{Flow rate} \leq 1.5 \text{ l/min}$$

$$30^\circ \leq \text{Collector angle} \leq 60^\circ \quad \text{and}$$

$$30^\circ \leq \text{Reflector angle} \leq 60^\circ$$

All the process variables were given equal importance and weightage. About 30 solutions were found by the software and based on the desirability the best combination of process variables was chosen and the corresponding response was noted as shown in [Table III](#).

TABLE III

OPTIMIZED VALUES OF PROCESS VARIABLES AND CORRESPONDING RESPONSES

Panel	Flow Rate	Collector Angle	Reflector Angle	Thermal Efficiency	Desirability	
Black-Chrome	1.28	43.89	44.92	89.3283	0.984	Selected
Ni-Co	1.32	46.91	42.34	79.246	0.974	Selected

IV. CONCLUSIONS

- The average thermal efficiency of Black Chrome coated panel without the reflector is 59.7% and with reflector is 81.3%. The average temperature difference is 21°C and 26°C.
- The average thermal efficiency of Nickel Cobalt coated panel without a reflector is 53.1% and with reflector is 59%. The average temperature difference is 14.5°C and 18.9°C.
- It is found by optimization that, the maximum thermal efficiency of 89.3% can be obtained at 1.28 l/min, 43.89°, and 44.92° for Black Chrome panel and Nickel Cobalt panel, the maximum thermal efficiency

is 79.2% at 1.32 l/min of flow rate, 46.91° of collector angle, and 42.34° of reflector angle.

- The maximum efficiency of the Black Chrome panel is 12.7% higher than the maximum efficiency of the Nickel Cobalt panel.

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